

////////////////////////////////////
**PRIMARY STUDY ON INFLUENCE OF FOOD PACKAGING
DESIGN BENEFITS ON BRAND ASSOCIATION FROM
CONSUMERS' VIEWS**

Shu-Yuan Lin*, Jen Yen**

Graduate School of Design, National Yunlin University of Science and Technology, Yunlin, Taiwan

* linsy@yuntech.edu.tw

** yenj@yuntech.edu.tw

ABSTRACT

Product packaging design is the approach with the most cost benefit for establishing brand equity. In severely competitive sales market, it will influence consumers' cognition, attitude, and preference toward brands and become the key factor of establishing of brand equity. As exploratory research, this study focuses on major dimensions (brand association) of brand equity to probe into the packaging design benefits that most influence brand association, as well as the composition categories of brand association that are easily influenced by packaging design benefits. Focus groups are conducted on consumers and analysis is based on qualitative data. Finally, the researcher indicates the most representative research propositions on influence of packaging design benefits on brand association as the criteria for development of research hypotheses.

Keywords: Brand association, Packaging design benefits.

INTRODUCTION

The packaging design becomes the image of the brand, consumers come to recognize and visually identify with the values, qualities, features, and attributes of the brand (Klimchuk, & Krasovec, 2006). Performance of packaging design determines consumers' evaluation of brands. The process, from selecting products on shelves, opening the packages, and using products to final recycling, influences brand experience. Packaging can be the subtle but complete demonstration of brands. This study suggests that when consumers perceive design benefits of packaging, such as the uniqueness

of packaging, it will lead to brand association. Therefore, once packaging design influences consumers' brand perception, what types of design are more influential? This is the question of this study.

The research scope refers to convenience goods and shopping goods in the food industry. Convenience goods provide consumers with rational and functional practical value. The sales channels are mostly retail stores. Shopping goods provide consumers with perceptual and pleasant feelings. The function of products is sometimes not the priority of consumers' purchase decision, as the channels are mostly stores, shops, or counters in department stores.

In this study, focus group interviews are conducted on consumers, as based on qualitative analysis. From the perspective of consumers, the researcher attempts to recognize composition categories of packaging design benefits and brand association, and further studies the relationship among the categories. For instance, in various design benefits, what are the categories that actively influence brand association? In addition, what are the composition categories of brand association that are influenced by packaging design benefits the most? The framework of this paper includes three sections. In the first section, by literature review on packaging design and brand association, the researcher reorganizes the possible composition categories of two dimensions. The outcome of this stage will be the criterion for Axial coding in focus group interviews. In the second section, the researcher will elaborate the steps of focus group interviews and the qualitative data analysis. Finally,

the research results will be analyzed and discussed, and related research propositions will be developed. This study aims to recognize the composition categories of dimensions and conceptual definitions and further probe into the possible relationships among categories. The relationships will be initially demonstrated according to interviews with consumers in order to result in research propositions. Cooper and Schindler (2008) define a proposition as a statement about observable phenomena (concepts) that may be judged as true or false. When a proposition is formulated for empirical testing, we call it a hypothesis. Therefore, this study emphasizes "discovery" rather than "validation" of research propositions.

COMPOSITION CATEGORIES OF BRAND ASSOCIATION

A brand association is anything "linked" in memory to a brand (Aaker, 1991). Therefore, the composition categories of brand association are broad. Aaker (1991) divided brand association into eleven categories, as follows: a) product attributes; b) intangibles; c) customer benefits; d) relative price; e) use/application; f) user/customer; g) celebrity/person; h) life-style/personality; i) product class; j) competitors; k) country/geographic area (p.114). Aaker also suggests that different associations reveal different intensities of characteristics. Keller (1993) proposed that brand associations can be classified into three major categories of increasing scope: attributes, benefits, and attitudes (p.4).

a) attributes association are those descriptive features that characterize a product or service. Product-related attributes are defined as the ingredients necessary for performing the product or service function sought by consumers. Non-product-related attributes are defined as external aspects of the product or service that relate to its purchase or consumption. The four main types of non-product-related attributes are price information, packaging or product appearance information, user imagery (i.e., what type of person uses the product or service), and usage imagery (i.e., where and in what types of situations the product or service is used).

b) benefits association are the personal value consumers attach to the product or service attributes -- that is, what consumers think the product or service can do for them. Benefits can be further distinguished into three categories according to the underlying motivations to which they relate (Park, Jaworski, & MacInnis, 1986): functional benefits, experiential benefits, and symbolic benefits. c) brand attitudes are defined as consumers' overall evaluations of a brand. Besides three major types of brand association (attributes, benefits, and attitudes), Keller (1991) consider five ways that secondary associations may be created for the brand, arising from primary attribute associations related to the company, the country of origin, the distribution channels, a celebrity spokesperson or endorser of the product or service, and an event. Moreover, Herr, Farquhar, and Fazio (1993) indicated that types of brand association include kinds of products, use situations, product attributes, and customer benefits. According to literature review, categories of brand associations, as indicated by scholars (Aaker, 1991; Herr, Farquhar, & Fazio, 1993; Keller, 1993), include the concept of perceived quality and consumers' overall perceived evaluation of products, which associations mostly refer to product attributes. Therefore, this study further supplements the possible categories in the association of product evaluation. Garvin's (1984) proposed dimensions of product quality include: a) performance, which refers to the primary operation characteristics of a product, b) features, "bells and whistles" that are often added to products, c) conformance, is a measure of consistency or a reflection of how well a product matches up against pre-established specifications, d) reliability, a reliable product can be counted on and the odds of its failing within a specified period are small, e) durability, which reflects the economic or physical life of a product, f) serviceability, a product's serviceability, or speed of repair is an important independent element in maintaining a quality image, g) aesthetics (fits and finishes), which refer to product looks, feels, sounds, tastes, or smells is clearly a matter of personal judgment, h) perceptions of quality, based on advertising or on

the excellence of other products produced by the company have a similar impact (p.41). Some items are evaluation association, which must be based on consumers' use of products. This study aims to probe into consumers' evaluation associations simply on packaging, and without using the products. Therefore, in eight categories, this study will not adopt evaluation association items, including product use experience, such as consistency or service competence. According to the views of 11 industrial experts, Yen and Lin (2010) probed into the possible categories of

brand association. The result shows 20 brand association categories, which include the concepts proposed by scholars above (Aaker, 1991; Garvin, 1984; Herr, Farquhar, & Fazio, 1993; Keller, 1993). Therefore, based on the conceptual definitions of these categories, the researcher attempts to determine if there are new categories from consumers' perspectives. The 20categories are divided into product-related attributes associations and non-product-related attributes associations. This study reorganizes the concepts and definitions of the categories in Table 1.

Brand association					
Product-related attributes association			Non-product-related attributes association		
Code	Category	Definition	Code	Category	Definition
1AS	Product sort association	Consumer association with product sort, main ingredients/components, flavor, and specifications.	11AS	Celebrity/person association	Consumer association with products' spokespersons or promoters.
2AS	Primary product characteristics association	Consumer association with beneficial functions of products. These are the main functions and benefits given to consumers, and are an imperative; for example: a dishwashing liquid's ability to cleanse or a diaper's ability to absorb.	12AS	Life-style/personality association	Consumer association with the target group of products; for example: a refrigerator designed for single people.
3AS	Subsidiary product characteristics association	Consumer association with the subsidiary beneficial functions of products. This refers to a product's additional functions and benefits that are non-imperative; for example: a dishwashing liquid for "sensitive skin".	13AS	Use/application association	Consumer association with application of products; for example: ice cream as dessert.
4AS	Reliability association	Consumer association with product reliability, credibility and perfection.	14AS	User/customer association	Consumer association with product users; for example: a shower gel for babies.
5AS	Durability association	Consumer association with product shelf-life, durability and preservability.	15AS	Country/geographic area association	Consumer association with products' country of origin; for example: French perfume and Japanese electronics.
6AS	Aesthetic association	Consumer association with the aesthetic presentation of products. This refers to the suitability of a product's exterior and interior, and its attention to detail.	16AS	Competitors association	Consumer association with products' competitors; for example: MacDonald's and KFC.
7AS	Perceived quality association	Consumer association with overall product perceived quality; for example: regarding innovation, high-quality and professionalism.	17AS	Company image association	Consumer association with products' companies.
8AS	Product class association	Consumer association with the relative class of a product among other similar products.	18AS	Store association	Consumer association with products' channels of distribution.
9AS	Quality-price association	Consumer association with the relative pricing of similar products.	19AS	Events association	Consumer association with activities and events related to products.
			20AS	Cultural association	Consumer association with the cultural background of products.
			21AS	Visual style association	Consumer association with the visual styles of products.

Table 1. Composition categories and conceptual definitions of brand association

COMPOSITION CATEGORIES OF PACKAGING DESIGN BENEFITS

This study defines packaging design benefits according to consumer orientation, which means that packaging designs can provide consumers with effects, benefits, or assistance., as such design effects meet consumers' needs upon consumers' purchase, carrying, taking apart, use, and after use. From the consumer's viewpoint, an effective package performs five value-added functions: a)

identify the brand; b) convey descriptive and persuasive information; c) facilitate product transportation and protection; d) assist at-home storage; e) aid product consumption (Bassin, 1988). James (1999) emphasized that aesthetic and functional performances of packaging are both important, and suggested equal value for packaging aesthetics and function. Among various kinds of information, packaging aesthetics draws consumers' attention. However, the packaging function must be

satisfying in order to lead to consumers' repurchase intentions. Regarding demands for packaging design, Lamb, Hair, and McDaniel (1999) indicated the following items for consumers: a) containing and protecting products, b) facilitating use and convenience, c) facilitating recycling and reducing environmental damage. According to the scholars above, benefits of packaging design for consumers include product protection, product information, use convenience, brand or product recognition, aesthetics, and environmental protection. However, this study is uncertain about other design benefits of packaging for consumers.

Yen and Lin (2010) pointed out that the packaging dimension included 13 categories, which also represent the design benefits that packaging can provide for consumers. The content includes the concepts suggested by other scholars. Therefore, this study will adopt these 13 design benefits and conceptual definitions. In this study, and by consumers' focus group interviews, the researcher attempts to discover new categories from the consumers' perspective. Categories and conceptual definitions of packaging design benefits are as shown in Table 2.

Packaging design benefits		
Code	Category	Definition
A	Cultural	Incorporating representative pictures and colors of localities and other cultural aspects into packaging design to showcase local cultural, humanities or ethnic characteristics.
B	Symbolic	Using the visual styles of packaging to reflect upon the psychological symbols of different social classes and hint at the consumer's lifestyle, ethnic qualities and identification within a certain social class.
C	Informative	The clear labeling of a product's relevant information, including product name, product content, product components, nutritional information, usage, expiration date, notable items, contact information, consumer service number, relevant accreditation information, barcode, brand slogan, brand imagery and product imagery. Also includes the production process and harvesting process of agricultural products.
D	Aesthetic	The aesthetic planning of the designer, including color, imagery, layout, printing material and packaging material.
E	Innovative	The originality and conceptualized representation of packaging design that is unlike anything that already exists regardless of color, imaging, printing effects, materials, style, structural formation or usability, and is different to the styles of fellow competitors; a unique packaging design.
F	Visibility	The ability to catch the eye of the consumer through visual presentation such as color, layout and structural formation, and emphasize the uniqueness of the product.
G	Identifiable	The ability to portray brand and product characteristics and sort so that it stands out among similar products through brand designs such as font, imagery, color, printing effects, packaging structure and materials, and the ability to trigger consumer association and recollection to establish correct brand recognition and product sort differentiation.
H	Systematic	A unified visual design that provides consumers with good brand and product sort identification to aid with the identification and packaging imagery of a series of products and accumulate the unified image of a brand to avoid confusion with similar products.
I	Memorable	The visual elements of packaging that include imagery, color and structural formation that create consumer memory of a brand or product, and continuously reinforce that image while the product is in use.
J	Protective	Packing material and structural formation must be safe and stable so that it can withstand various external environments to ensure product quality and stability in production, transfer, placement and application.
K	Convenient	The ability of the packaging structural formation to convenience consumers in carrying, opening, resealing and storage.
L	Environmental	The ability of packaging to meet environmental needs such as avoiding over-packaging, having reusable qualities, having good use of space, being made with recyclable natural materials and as little special printing as possible so that the packaging is bio-degradable and wastes little energy in its time of use.
M	Displayable qualities	Good display qualities of a product include being able to be displayed and stacked with ease so that the contents of the product may be shown.

Table 2. Composition categories and conceptual definitions of packaging design benefits. (From "A study of the variables of packaging design that affect brand equity" by J. Yen, & S. Y. Lin, (2010). *Journal of Design*, Vol. 15, No. 1, 81.)

INFLUENCE OF PACKAGING DESIGN ON BRAND ASSOCIATION

Aaker (1991) pointed out that brand image is a set of association, usually organized into groups that have meaning. In a similar sense, Biel (1992) revealed that a good starting point is to describe the image of a brand as that cluster of attributes and associations that consumers connect to the brand name. Therefore, brand association upon packaging design will indirectly influence the construction of brand image. Often, one of the

strongest associations consumers have with a brand is inspired by the look of its packaging. The package can become an important means of brand recognition and convey or imply information to build or reinforce valuable brand association (Keller, 1998). The connection of associations will develop the brand image. Therefore, packaging design is closely related to brand image construction. Southgate (1994) suggested that packaging will enhance the establishment of brand image, and builds the relationship between the consumer and the product (Klimchuk, & Krasovec, 2006). In recent

years, many firms gradually realize that well-designed packaging can immediately construct consumers' brand image and increase sales (Kotler et al., 1999).

METHOD

RESEARCH DESIGN

By literature review, the researcher initially reorganizes the composition categories of brand association, and packaging design benefits, also indicates the categories and related conceptual definitions in Tables 1 and 2 as the criteria of conceptual clustering and generalization in consumers' focus group interviews. From consumers' perspective, this study attempts to

determine new category in order to completely construct the categories of dimensions, and conducts primary exploration on relationship between categories. Descriptions of the research steps are as shown below.

Focus groups

- Participants' backgrounds
- Focus groups aim to elaborate the influence of packaging design benefits on brand association regarding convenience goods and shopping goods in the food industry. By purposive sampling, the researcher selects participants. Finally, there are 18 consumers participating in the interviews, with backgrounds as shown in Table 3.

Demographic variables	Variable level	Number of people	Variable level	Number of people	Variable level	Number of people
Gender	Male	9	Female	9		
Age	20-29 years old	5	30-39 years old	2		
	40-49 years old	6	50-59 years old	5		
Residential locations	Central Taiwan	11	Southern Taiwan	5	Northern Taiwan	2
Educational level	Junior high school	2	Senior high school	3	University	8
	Graduate school	4	Doctor	1		
Monthly income	Below 10,000	7	10,001-20,000	2	20,001-30,000	1
	30,001-40,000	2	40,001-50,000	2	50,001-60,000	2
	Over 60,001	2				

Table 3. Basic information of focus groups participants.

- Steps of focus group interviews
- Step 1:** Description of topics: The host clearly suggests that the purpose of this meeting is to discuss the influence of packaging design benefits on brand association of convenience foods and shopping foods.
- Step 2:** Open coding: The host guides the participants to write their views, opinions, and experience regarding the topics on the paper cards, and asks them to only indicate one conceptual sentence on the card. In concept development, the host encourages each participant to share their concepts to trigger new ideas.
- Step 3:** Axial coding: Axial coding aims to generalize the same concepts within the same group in order to result in categories. The host attaches paper cards with the titles of categories to the white board and invites all participants to attach their concept cards below the related titles of category, according to the definition of categories in Tables 1, 2, and the item of conceptual definitions. When participants cannot generalize the concepts to these categories, the concepts are viewed as independent

and become new category. At this stage, the composition categories of packaging design benefits and brand association will be confirmed.

Step 4: Construction of Categories Relationship Table, CRT. By theoretical code, Participants are asked to judge the influences of packaging design effect categories on brand association categories in the matrix tables and indicate the arrows sign in the matrix tables of categories relationship. The table is shown as Table 4.

Brand association	Aesthetic association	Quality-price association
Packaging design benefits		
Culture	↑	
...		

Table 4. The form of Categories Relationship Table, CRT. (For example, participants suggest the influence of culture on Aesthetic association by arrow sign "↑". Therefore, a pair of category relationship is recognized by participants.)

Steps of qualitative analysis

Data analysis is conducted on the Categories Relationship Table (CRT), as obtained from focus group interviews.

- **Step 1:** Construction of Theoretical Code Frequency Table, TCFT.

Assume that each member of the focus group has completed an individual Categories Relationship Table (CRT). The first step in calculating frequencies is to record the total number of votes for each relationship in Theoretical Code Frequency Table (TCFT). Corresponding pair category relationships of the arrow sign “↗” in the CRT indicates the number of people, among 18 participants, who agree with the relationship. The figures are marked in the table of the original arrows sign, as shown in Table 5.

Brand association	Aesthetic association	Quality-price association
↗ Packaging design benefits		
Culture	10	
...		

Table 5. The form of Theoretical Code Frequency Table, TCFT. (Where “10” means 10 participants agree with the influence of culture on Aesthetic association).

- **Step 2:** Power analysis on theoretical code frequency.

A reasonably rigorous and powerful technique for achieving and documenting the degree of consensus in a focus group is based on the Pareto Principle. The Pareto Principle states that something like 20% of the variables in a system will account for 80% of the total variation in outcomes (Northcutt, & McCoy, 2004). The essential utility of the Pareto Principle is this: A minority of the relationships in any system will account for a majority of the variation within the system. Based on this theoretical concept, this study accumulates the frequency of participants recognizing all pair category relationships, and obtains the most representative relationships by power analysis.

- **Step 3:** Follow up individual interviews with focus group participants.

Through power analysis on theoretical code frequency, the researcher extracts the most critical and representative relationships, and invites the participants from focus groups to describe their views, through individual interviews, and the data will be transcribed as a transcript. By open coding, axial coding, and theoretical code, the relationships between categories are connected as a demonstration of relationships in the development of research propositions.

- **Step 4:** Development of research propositions. Based on the most representative relationships upon power analysis, the researcher indicates the influences of packaging design benefits on brand association. Finally, the relationships that are recognized by the most participants are developed into research propositions. Individual interview transcripts with participants support the research propositions.

RESEARCH RESULT ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

DEVELOPMENT OF NEW CATEGORIES

According to the outcomes of consumers’ focus group interviews, the dimensions of packaging design benefits are not developed into new categories. It demonstrates that 13 design benefits of literature review are the developed information. As to brand association dimensions, two new categories are developed: “sales association” (code: 10AS) and “designer association” (code: 22AS). Sales association means consumers associate the products with good sales or other content related to sales. Designer association means consumers associate product packaging with the possible designers. Therefore, categories of brand association dimensions increase from the 20 found in literature reviews to 22.

ANALYSIS ON INFLUENCE OF PACKAGING DESIGN BENEFITS ON BRAND ASSOCIATION

Power analysis on theoretical code frequency

Frequency of each relationship is determined and recorded on a spreadsheet by tallying all of the relationships from the CRTs (Categories Relationship Table). The total number of “votes” for each relationship is calculated, and the relationships are sorted out in descending order. Cumulative percentages are then calculated for each relationship, which is to say a *Pareto Chart* is constructed.

Table 6 shows that a total of 1923 votes were cast for a total of 156 possible relationships. The next step is to sort the relationships in descending order of frequency and to calculate cumulative frequencies and percentages in terms of both the total number of relationships (156) as well as the

total number of votes (1923, which is a proxy for the total variation in the system).

Item	Category Pair Relationship	Frequency Sorted (Descending)	Cumulative Frequency	Cumulative Percent (Relation)	Cumulative Percent (Frequency)	Power
1.	A→7AS	17	17	0.6	0.9	0.2
2.	D→21AS	17	34	1.3	1.8	0.5
3.	C→4AS	16	50	1.9	2.6	0.7
4.	A→6AS	16	66	2.6	3.4	0.9
5.	B→9AS	16	82	3.2	4.3	1.1
6.	D→12AS	16	98	3.8	5.1	1.3
7.	A→15AS	16	114	4.5	5.9	1.4
8.	A→20AS	16	130	5.1	6.8	1.6
9.	A→21AS	16	146	5.8	7.6	1.8
10.	A→1AS	15	161	6.4	8.4	2.0
⋮						
67.	D→1AS	12	947	42.9	49.2	6.3
68.	G→1AS	12	959	43.6	49.9	6.3
69.	L→1AS	12	971	44.2	50.5	6.3
70.	B→2AS	12	983	44.9	51.1	6.2
71.	F→2AS	12	995	45.5	51.7	6.2
⋮						
155.	D→22AS	10	1914	99.4	99.5	0.2
156.	D→2AS	9	1923	100	100	0.0
Total Frequency	1923					

Table 6. Categories in descending order of frequency with Pareto and Power Analysis.

In Table 6, the column of *Category Pair Relationship* indicates the codes of the relationships (for instance, A→7AS denotes the influence of “cultural” on “perceived quality association”). The column of *Frequency Sorted* refers to the number of participants that agree with different relationships. *Cumulative Frequency*: Entries in this column contain the running total or cumulative frequency. Each entry is the frequency of votes cast for a category pair added to the previous total. *Cumulative Percent (Relation)*: This is a cumulative percentage based on the number of total possible relationships, in this case, 156; that is, each relationship represents 1/156 or approximately 0.6% of the total possible number. This cumulative percentage is one of two factors in the Power index. *Cumulative Percent (Frequency)*: This is a cumulative percentage based on the number of votes cast (1923). Each entry is the percentage of votes cast for a category pair added to the previous total. *Power*: Power is an index of the degree of optimization of the system and is simply the difference between *Cumulative Percent (Frequency)* and *Cumulative Percent (Relation)*.

Explained powers of the figures continue to increase from the first relationship (A→7AS) to the 69th relationship (L→1AS) (from 0.2 to 6.3). From the

70th relationship (B→2AS), the explanatory power begins to decline, meaning the 69th relationship is the threshold of the best explanatory power. True to Pareto Principle, we find that relatively few of the possible 69 relationships account for most of the variance. The first 69 (44.2% of the total) account for 50.5% of the total variation. Therefore, 69 relationships would be a defensible choice for explanation the influence relationships of packaging design benefits on brand association.

Brand association includes 22 categories. According to the outcome of power analysis, celebrity/person association, competitors association, and store association are insignificantly related to packaging design benefits. After power analysis, these three categories are eliminated from the representative data. Therefore, in data simplification, the above 3 items are eliminated and categories of brand association are converged into 19 items.

Categories with the most significant influences in packaging design benefits

Positions of 69 pair category relationships are as shown in Table 7, which horizontally accumulates the number of relationships (↕) between simplex design benefit and overall brand association. It indicates the influence of design benefits by figures of “accumulated number of relationships”. When the accumulated figure is above or equal to 6, it is treated as a design benefit with significant influence, meaning that the design benefit can influence 1/3 of the total items of brand association. Thus, from packaging design benefits, the researcher extracts 6 design benefits with significant influences: cultural, aesthetics, symbolic, innovative, informative, and systematic.

Brand association categories with the most influenced by design benefits

This study accumulates the number of relationships between brand association categories and overall packaging design benefits, which are presented in “accumulated number of relationships” in Table 8. When accumulated figure is above or equal to 4, it means brand association categories can be easily influenced by packaging design benefits, meaning that 1/3 of the 13 packaging design benefits can influence them. Therefore, this study extracts 6 categories from brand association: product sort

association, perceived quality association, company image association, reliability association, aesthetics association, and product class association. In comparison to other categories, they are easily influenced by packaging design benefits.

The most representative pair category relationships

This study discovers the 69 most representative relationships between packaging design benefits and brand association. In order to focus on the discussion, the researcher only elaborates the relationships that are recognized by at least 16

participants, from which 9 are relationships obtained(The first 9 relationships in Table 6): Cultural→perceived quality association, Cultural→ aesthetic association, Cultural→country/geographic area association, Cultural→cultural association, Cultural→visual style association, Aesthetic→visual style association, Aesthetic→life-style/personality association, Informative→reliability association, and Systematic→quality-price association. This study will develop research propositions regarding these 9 categories.

Brand association	Product-related attributes association										Non-product-related attributes association										The total of accumulated relationships
	Product sort (1AS)	Primary product characteristics (2AS)	Subsidiary product characteristics (3AS)	Reliability (4AS)	Durability (5AS)	Aesthetic (6AS)	Perceived quality (7AS)	Product class (8AS)	Quality-price (9AS)	Sales (10AS)	Life-style/personality (12AS)	User/application (13AS)	User/customer (14AS)	Country/geographic area (15AS)	Company image (17AS)	Events (19AS)	Cultural (20AS)	Visual style (21AS)	Designer (22AS)		
Cultural (A)	↑			↑		↑	↑	↑		↑	↑	↑	↑	↑		↑	↑		11		
Aesthetic (D)	↑			↑		↑	↑	↑		↑	↑	↑	↑	↑		↑	↑		11		
Symbolic (B)	↑						↑	↑		↑	↑	↑	↑	↑					9		
Innovative (E)	↑						↑	↑		↑		↑		↑				↑	8		
Informative (C)	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑									↑	↑				7		
Systematic (H)	↑			↑			↑	↑		↑					↑				6		
Identifiable (G)	↑			↑			↑	↑		↑					↑				5		
Memorable (I)	↑	↑					↑	↑					↑						5		
Environmental (L)	↑			↑										↑					3		
Visibility (F)	↑						↑												2		
Protective (J)					↑														1		
Displayable (M)						↑													1		
Convenient (K)																			0		
69																					

Table 7. The influence of packaging design benefits on brand association. (The most representative relationships in Categories Relationship Table)

Brand association	Product sort (1AS)	Perceived quality (7AS)	Company image (17AS)	Reliability (4AS)	Aesthetic (6AS)	Product class (8AS)	Quality-price (9AS)	Sales (10AS)	Life-style/personality (12AS)	User/application (13AS)	User/customer (14AS)	Cultural (20AS)	Visual style (21AS)	Primary product characteristics (2AS)	Durability (5AS)	Country/geographic area (15AS)	Events (19AS)	Subsidiary product characteristics (3AS)	Designer (22AS)
Cultural (A)	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑			↑	↑	↑	↑	↑			↑			
Aesthetic (D)	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑		↑	↑	↑	↑	↑						
Symbolic (B)	↑	↑	↑			↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑						
Innovative (E)	↑	↑	↑			↑	↑				↑	↑							↑
Informative (C)	↑		↑	↑										↑	↑	↑		↑	
Systematic (H)	↑	↑		↑		↑		↑									↑		
Identifiable (G)	↑	↑	↑	↑				↑											
Memorable (I)	↑	↑	↑								↑			↑					
Environmental (L)	↑		↑	↑															
Visibility (F)	↑	↑																	
Protective (J)															↑				
Displayable (M)					↑														
Convenient (K)																			
Accumulated number of relationships	10	8	8	6	4	4	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	1	1	1
The total of accumulated relationships	69																		

Table 8. The influence of packaging design benefits on brand association. (The most representative relationships in Categories Relationship Table)

Development of research propositions

Participants' individual interviews initially support nine research propositions. In Table 9, the different fonts indicate the important transcripts text. According to the conceptual definitions of packaging design benefits (Table 2), and the definitions of brand association categories (Table 1), the concepts are connected. According to the participants' suggestions, the researcher recognizes the relationships between two categories, which demonstrate their correlation. According to 9 representative category relationships, participants mostly suggest that cultural performance in packaging design benefits can create perceived quality association, aesthetics association, country of origin association, cultural association, and visual style association. Packaging design interprets culture and time (Gobé, 2001). In order to allow the overall images of products to meet the regions, packaging includes local featured images, local materials and colors preferred by local consumers in the design in order to highlight local cultural characteristics, human characteristics, or group culture. Interpretation of local culture triggers consumers' affection, enhances the relationship between brands and consumers, and creates cultural value added. The technique not only reinforces overall value perceptions and aesthetic experiences of brands, but also creates

rich visual style perceptions, thus, consumers will be impressed. Cultural performance of packaging usually empathize possible countries or regions of origin of products. Consumers thus have the related association and the image and evaluation of the country or region will be involved in the brands, which can highlight the images of brands. In addition, aesthetic performance of packaging on visual style association and users' life style and personal associations, informative on reliability association, and symbolic performance on quality price association are generally recognized by participants. The packaging design visually articulates the brand's promise, whether it is quality, value, performance, safety, or convenience (Klimchuk, & Krasovec, 2006). This takes place when certain associations relevant to the product are called up in the consumer's mind by the packaging design (Riezebos, Kist, & Kootstra, 2003). Southgate (1994) describes two different roles that packaging can play in the brand development process, namely a passive and an active role. The essence of an active role for packaging is that the packaging design itself (actively) contributes to the brand image. When packaging triggers richer brand associations of consumers, the image and characteristics of the brand will be reinforced, thus, consumers will be impressed.

Research proposition 1: Cultural performance of packaging design influences perceived quality association			
Packaging design benefits category	Interview transcript	Brand association category	Number of files
Cultural	<i>~ They manufacture packages of culture of the National Palace Museum for Chinese tourists. For instance, on a small package of rice, a Jadeite Cabbage and a meat-shaped stone are printed. Three packages (one and half catty) cost NT\$520. However, people still buy them for decoration. They look valuable.</i>	<u>Perceived quality association</u>	I-01 (62:63)
Research proposition 2: Cultural performance of packaging design influences aesthetics association.			
Category	Interview transcript	Category	Number of files
Cultural	<i>They manufacture packages of culture of the National Palace Museum for Chinese tourists. For instance, on a small package of rice, a Jadeite Cabbage and meat-shaped stone are printed. Three packages (one and half catty) cost NT\$520. However, people still buy them for decoration. They look valuable. I also like to buy them, not just for eating the rice. It is for the packaging. It is beautiful and I will have the intention to purchase-</i>	<u>Aesthetic association</u>	I-10 (62:64)
Research proposition 3: Cultural performance of packaging design influences country and region of origin			
Category	Interview transcript	Category	Number of files
Cultural	<i>It seems that the package is from Japan, since they are designed as packages in that country, such as Japanese patterns and cherry blossoms. It seems that the products are imported from Japan.</i>	<u>Country and region of origin association</u>	I-03 (142:144)
Research proposition 4: Cultural performance of packaging design influences cultural association			
Category	Interview transcript	Category	Number of files

Cultural	<i>Red flower cotton prints are used as packaging. It reminds me of my childhood. My mother wrapped lunch boxes in this kind of cloth. I recall my childhood. Nowadays, the cloth is popular.</i>	<u>Cultural association</u>	I-08 (98:99)
Research proposition 5: Cultural performance of packaging design influences visual style association.			
Category	Interview transcript	Category	Number of files
Cultural	<i>When I last visited Kinmen, I saw some packages with pictures of local architecture on them. It looks historical and traditional.</i>	<u>Visual style association</u>	I-03 (55:56)
Research proposition 6: Aesthetic performance of packaging design influences visual style association.			
Category	Interview transcript	Category	Number of files
aesthetics	<i>Packaging of White Wood House looks elegant. It is refined and high class.</i>	<u>Visual style association</u>	I-01 (97:97)
Research proposition 7: Aesthetic performance of packaging design influences users' life style and personality association.			
Category	Interview transcript	Category	Number of files
Aesthetics	<i>When packaging is well designed, the products will look high-class. It seems that we have better taste and class-</i>	<u>Users' life style and personality association</u>	I-07 (31:33)
Research proposition 8: Informative of packaging design influences reliability association.			
Category	Interview transcript	Category	Number of files
Informative	<i>Part of the packaging is transparent and I can see the contents. Thus, I can compare the products. I will not consider products totally covered, as I will question them..</i>	<u>Reliability association</u>	I-10 (102:104)
Research proposition 9: Symbolic performance of packaging design influences quality price association.			
Category	Interview transcript	Category	Number of files
Symbolic	<i>-When I hold a coffee cup, I will show the mark of Starbucks since I feel high- class in this way- Others will consider the coffee as more expensive, not the coffee which costs NT\$50 in convenience stores.</i>	<u>Quality price association</u>	I-01 (32:35)

Table 9. Theoretical code of packaging design benefits on brand association

GENERAL DISCUSSION

Packaging is the most specific and direct demonstration of brands, which is not only an important asset of brand equity, but also an important tool to further construct brand equity. Many literatures suggest the importance of packaging for creating brand association; however, they cannot further indicate the design, which is more influential. Based on qualitative and data analysis results of this study, this paper further suggests the composition categories of packaging design benefits and brand association, as well as the design benefits that have more aggressive influence in the relationship between packaging design benefits and brand association, resulting in more brand association contents being triggered. On the other hand, this paper also proposes the items of brand association that are more likely to be generated under the influence of the overall packaging design benefits. The specific research results are as follows:

The composition categories of packaging design benefits and brand association

- 1) Food packaging design refers to 13 design benefits for consumers: informative, memorable, identifiable, culture, symbolic, aesthetics, innovative, visibility, systematic, displayable qualities, protective, convenient, and environmental. The items are the same as the 13 benefits suggested from experts' perspectives in the research of Yen and Lin (2010), which demonstrates that there are 13 benefits from the perspectives of experts and consumers.
- 2) In addition to the 20 categories of literature review, from the consumer view, this researcher further discovers two categories of brand association: sales association and designer association; therefore, brand association includes 22 categories. Product-Related Attributes Association refers to product sort association, primary product characteristics association, subsidiary product characteristics

association, reliability association, durability association, aesthetic association, perceived quality association, product class association, quality-price association, and sales association. Non-product attribute association includes celebrity/person association, life-style/personality association, use/application association, user/customer association, country/geographic area association, competitors association, company image association, store association, events association, cultural association, visual style association, and designer association. This study also demonstrates that packaging design benefits on celebrity/person association, competitors association, and store association are insignificant.

Analytical result of influences of categories

Table 10 demonstrates that the categories with the most significant influences on packaging design benefits, categories of brand association are easily influenced by packaging design benefits. The research results specifically indicate the critical categories of dimensions, which can function as the criterion for constructing related variables in future empirical research.

Packaging design benefits on brand association	
Categories with significant influence	Categories which are passively influenced
Cultural	Product sort association
Aesthetic	Perceived quality association
Symbolic	Company image association
Innovative	Reliability association
Informative	Aesthetics association
Systematic	Product class association.

Table 10. Analysis of important categories.

Development of research propositions

Research findings demonstrate that 13 categories of packaging design benefits influence all composition categories of brand association. However, in order to centralize the research scope, this study only indicates the relationships that are most recognized by consumers, and turns them into research propositions. Focus group participants' individual interviews support the research propositions, which demonstrate that, for consumers, relationships among the categories do exist. In future empirical

study plans, operational definitions of research propositions will be constructed to turn them into epistemologically corresponding variables (ECV). Through the establishment of research hypotheses and a collection of a greater amount of consumer data, the researcher attempts to validate the hypotheses.

REFERENCES

Aaker, D. A. (1991). *Managing brand equity: Capitalizing on the value of a brand name*. New York: The Free Press.

Bassin, S. B. (1988). Value-added packaging cuts through store clutter. *Marketing News*, Vol. 22, No. 20, 21.

Biel, L. A. (1992). How brand image drives brand equity. *Journal of Advertising Research*, Vol. 32, No. 6, RC6-12.

Cooper, D. R., & Schindler, P. S. (2008). *Business research methods* (10th ed.). Boston :McGraw-Hill Irwin.

Garvin, D. A. (1984). Product quality: An important strategic weapon. *Business Horizons*, Vol. 27, No. 3, 40-43.

Gobé, M. (2001). *Emotional branding: the new paradigm for connecting brands to people*. New York : Allworth Press.

Herr, P. M., Farquhar, M. M., & Fazio, R. H. (1993). *Using dominance measures to evaluate brand extensions* (Report #93-120). Cambridge, MA: Marketing Science Institute.

James, W. P. (1999). Five steps to packaging that sells. *Brand Packaging*, Vol.3, No. 4, 3.

Keller, K. L. (1993). Conceptualizing, measuring, and managing customer-based brand equity. *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 57, No. 1, 1-22.

Keller, K. L. (1998). *Strategic brand management: building, measuring, and managing brand equity*. Prentice-Hall.

Keller, K. L. (1991). *Conceptualizing, Measuring, and Managing Customer-Based Brand Equity*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Marketing Science Institute.

Klimchuk, M. R., & Krasovec, S. A. (2006). *Packaging design: Successful product branding from concept to shelf*. New Jersey: John Wiley & sons.

Kotler, P., Armstrong, G., Saunders, J., & Wong, V. (1999). *Principles of marketing*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.

Lamb, C. W., Hair, J. F., & McDaniel, C. (1999). *Essentials of marketing*. Cincinnati, Ohio : South-Western College Pub..

Northcutt, N., & McCoy, D. (2004). *Interactive qualitative analysis : A systems method for qualitative research*. Thousand Oaks, CA : Sage.

Park, C. W., Jaworski, B. J., & MacInnis, D. J. (1986). Strategic brand concept-image management. *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 50, No. 4, 135-145.

Riezebos, R., Kist, B., & Kootstra, G. (2003). *Brand Management : A Theoretical and Practical Approach*. Imprint: Harlow , New York : Financial Times/Prentice Hall.

Southgate, P. (1994). *Total branding by design: How to make your brand' s packaging more effective*. London: Kogan Page.

Yen, J., & Lin, S. Y. (2010). A study of the variables of packaging design that affect brand equity. *Journal of Design*, Vol. 15, No. 1, 71-91.